

WIND VALUE

An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

**End of Life Decisions for Wind Farms:
An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities**

**Social Media and Website Report 1
Deliverable 1.2**

Report on Month 6/48, August 2022

Author: Peter Deeney, University College Cork

IRC*21/PATH-A/9348 Peter Deeney SFI-IRC Pathway Prog

October 27, 2023

Contents

- Executive Summary** **1**

- 1 Introduction** **2**

- 2 Social Media** **2**
 - 2.1 Metrics and Targets 2
 - 2.2 Results 2

- 3 Website** **3**
 - 3.1 Metrics and Targets 3
 - 3.2 Results 3

- 4 Conclusion** **3**

The DOI for this report is **10.5281/zenodo.10049075**.

Executive Summary

This research project seeks to estimate a financial valuation for onshore wind farms in Ireland. It will develop decision support tools which will assist wind farm managers to decide between decommissioning, repowering and life-extension for the end-of-life of a wind farm. This research will also assist local communities who may be interested in buying part or all of their local wind farm.

A social media channel, Twitter [@windvalue](https://twitter.com/windvalue) and a website <https://windvalue.ie/> were set up to help to disseminate the output of the project and to facilitate engagement with stakeholders. Both the social media and website activity exceeded their targets for August 2022.

1 Introduction

The project's Twitter Account [@windvalue](#) (see Figure 1) and website <https://windvalue.ie/> (see Figure 2), were set up to disseminate the output of the project and to facilitate engagement with stakeholders. In order to make the best use of these channels of communication, both accounts were used to highlight topical news items and items of interest so as to attract interaction from stakeholders and the public. This approach appears to have been successful. The website has also shown itself to be very useful for organizing the End-of-Life Issues for Onshore Windfarms conference (27th May 2022), by allowing a web page and a custom email address to be set up for the conference.

2 Social Media

2.1 Metrics and Targets

As specified in the funding application, the number of Twitter followers will be the metric used to chart the progress of the project's social media outreach.

2.2 Results

The Wind Value Twitter account attracted 162 followers by 30th August 2022, the target was 100, (see Figure 1). This was probably due to a policy of mentioning other research groups and interested parties in Tweets.

Figure 1: Twitter Screenshot 30 Aug 2022

3 Website

3.1 Metrics and Targets

As specified in the funding application, the number site visits is the metric used to chart the progress of the project website. These were measured Blacknight, the company which hosts the website, using Webalizer Version 2.21. The numbers reported all visits, and visits from secure URLs only. It is common practice for more serious websites to obtain secure URL addresses. It is also common for many browsers to avoid sites without such accreditation. A screenshot of the front page of the website may be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Screenshot of Wind Value Website in March 2023

3.2 Results

The target for visits by the end of August 2022 was to 200, the number of visits by secure URLs was 8,326 (see Figure 3 and from all URLs, 11,655. This was almost certainly due to the Twitter site sending interested people to the website. It is notable that there was a peak in May 2022 due to the End-of-Life Issues for Onshore Windfarms conference. Also, the website was continually updated with news and other items of interest regarding wind energy in Ireland. An example of such an item of interest, "Cleaning Wind Turbine Blades Using Lasers", is seen in Figure 2.

4 Conclusion

The social media outreach and the website are exceeding their targets. While this is encouraging it does not mean that improvements cannot be made by perhaps using other channels of social media in the future or improving the content on the website.

Usage Statistics for d1696163-140738.blacknighthosting.com

Summary by Month
Generated 31-Aug-2022 17:55 IST

Summary by Month										
Month	Daily Avg					Monthly Totals				
	Hits	Files	Pages	Visits	Sites	KBytes	Visits	Pages	Files	Hits
Aug 2022	117	107	63	37	509	121810	1154	1959	3317	3641
Jul 2022	105	98	54	38	469	96205	1185	1692	3059	3268
Jun 2022	188	140	104	44	430	156540	1330	3147	4203	5660
May 2022	278	263	103	76	1132	260860	2380	3210	8159	8618
Apr 2022	178	145	59	43	592	137783	1306	1798	4379	5340
Mar 2022	161	127	63	29	390	186597	881	1917	3823	4832
Totals						959795	8236	13723	26940	31359

Generated by [Webalizer Version 2.21](#)

Figure 3: Screenshot of Website Statistics from Secure URLs, 31st August 2022